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**Promoting a Circular Economy through Plastic Recycling: Feasibility and
Environmental Impact of Plastic Brick Use in Abuja, Nigeria.**

MSc in Green Economy

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ABSTRACT

Plastic is ubiquitous and with its non-biodegradable properties, it can persist in nature for thousands of years. Plastic waste causes air, soil and water pollution which is hazardous to both terrestrial and aquatic species and harmful to human health. With a focus on Nigeria's capital city, Abuja, this research shows that plastic waste can be recycled to form plastic bricks which promote a circular economy and protects the environment while providing employment and solving the city's housing deficits. A mixed methodology approach which combined an extensive literature review and interviews of participants in the recycling, real estate and finance sectors was used to determine the environmental effect, social impact, feasibility and possible adoption of plastic bricks as building materials in Abuja. Previous studies show that plastic bricks reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by curbing fossil fuel and cement use and reducing landfilling and burning of plastic waste. With compressive strength of 2700kgf/cm² and moisture content and water absorption of 0.74% and 0.92% respectively, plastic bricks are proven to be stronger and more durable than sandcrete bricks. Plastic bricks are also light weight, eco-conservative, anti-seismic, resistant to extreme temperatures and bullet-proof. Abuja faces housing deficit due to high housing costs and with a 34% reduced cost against standard bricks, this research indicates that plastic brick will be attractive to investors and provide affordable housing to displaced persons (IDPs) in Abuja. To facilitate the acceptance of plastic bricks, there is need for sensitization of all stakeholders, interventions from government and funding from private and public institutions. It is concluded that adopting plastic brick in Abuja can promote sustainable socio-economic change, revolutionize the built environment space and aid actualization of Nigeria's climate change mitigation commitments.

KEYWORDS

Waste Management; Greenhouse Gas Emissions; Plastic Waste, Recycling, Plastic Brick

ABBREVIATIONS

SUPs	Single Use Plastics
MMt	Million Metric Tons
PET	Polyethylene Terephthalate
GHG	Greenhouse Gas Emissions
IDPs	Internally Displaced Persons
SSI	Semi-structured Interview
MSW	Municipal Solid Waste
Mt	Million tons
PSW	Plastic Solid Waste
FCTA	Federal Capital Territory Administration
AWB	Abuja Water Board
AGIS	Abuja Geographical Information System
AEPB	Abuja Environmental Protection Board
FCC	Federal Capital City
CBN	Central Bank of Nigeria

HIGHLIGHTS

- Mismanagement of plastic waste results in health issues and soil, water and air pollution.
- Recycling is critical for control of plastic waste in Abuja.
- Studies show that plastic bricks are stronger, durable and cheaper than standard bricks and can be used to provide affordable housing for low-income communities.
- Plastic bricks are environmentally friendly and reduce GHG emissions from plastic burning, landfills and cement use
- Acceptability for plastic bricks is fostered through the sensitization of all stakeholders and funding by the government and other institutions.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The flexibility, durability and resilience of plastics makes it a very inexpensive and common place solution to varying needs. Plastics have facilitated convenience and innovation and are being used in every area of life, from disposable food containers to durable goods such as appliances, electronics, high density polyethylene bottles, construction and medical equipment. Due to urbanization and population growth in developing and emerging economies, the use and application of plastics is increasing, including the demand and manufacture of single use plastics (SUPs), which continues to increase due to its very short useful life (Verma et al., 2016; Duru et al., 2019; Haque, 2019; Silva et al., 2021). For instance, more than 380 million metric tons (MMt) of plastic was produced world-wide in 2015, against 2 million metric tons (MMt) produced in 1950 (Azoulay et al., 2019). Plastics have also been identified as significant contributors to solid waste, contributing 10% of municipal solid waste generated globally (Thompson et al., 2009). Chapter 3 discusses the different components of solid waste and how plastic waste is generally managed across the globe.

Plastics are made to be very durable and extremely resistant to natural biodegradation, thus, they can persist in the environment for many years. The lifespan of plastics can range from 450 years for Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET) bottles, medical face masks and grocery bags to as much as 5,000 years for Extruded Polystyrene Foam (Arumugam, 2020; Bio-tech Environmental, 2019). This non-biodegradable nature of plastics has made it a significant contributor to the present global environmental crises. Plastics pose an alarming threat to natural ecosystems and human health. They cause air, land and marine pollution, energy waste, biodiversity breakdowns, food chain contamination and economic loss (Haque, 2019; Verma et al., 2016). Chapter 3 discusses extensively, the harmful effects of plastics and how it pollutes the environment, threatens marine wildlife and enters the food chain.

In Africa, plastic waste is posing a major environmental issue, mostly because of high proportions of mismanaged plastic wastes and lack of recycling facilities. Chapter 3 discusses how Nigeria is contributing significantly to the plastic waste scourge in Africa. Previous studies by Babayemi et al. (2019) and Jambeck et al. (2015), identify Nigeria as the 2nd largest importer of plastic polymers in

Africa and the 9th largest contributor to plastic waste in the world. Most Nigerian cities are producing tremendous amounts of plastic waste and are discussed further in Chapter 3. These wastes are disposed of indiscriminately or burnt on the streets, thereby causing release of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, health problems and air, water and soil contamination. Plastic waste has also been implicated in wildfires and blocking of water channels and drainages leading to flooding in major cities. With a teeming population of over 200 million, a population growth rate of 2.37% and increased demand of SUPs due to the Covid 19 pandemic, it is inevitable that plastic waste and its resultant effects in Nigeria will continue to rise significantly (Duru et al., 2019; Chen et al., 2019; UN DESA, 2019). This is further worsened by provision of efficient waste management amenities and absence of government policies on production of SUPs as practiced in countries such as Kenya, Rwanda South Africa and Somalia, who have either placed a total ban on plastic bags or heavily regulate plastic products (Dumbili and Henderson, 2020).

Chapter 3 discusses how recycling is the most efficient plastic waste management method because of its multiplier effects of waste management, resource conservation and economic benefits such as wealth and job creation (Olanrewaju and Oyebade, 2019; Babayemi et al., 2019; Kehinde et al., 2020). Plastic waste can be reused, used to generate electricity or fuel oil. It can also be recycled to produce materials such as polyester for clothing, intricate art designs or as additives or reinforcements in construction. With millions of tons of plastic waste being produced daily in Nigeria, and no major disposal or recycling programs in place, it has become a necessity to adopt innovative recycling programs in a bid to ameliorate the plastic waste menace threatening to engulf the country. This research specifically looks at the feasibility and environmental benefits of plastic waste recycling into bricks for construction in Nigeria, using Abuja, the city capital, as a case study.

1.1 RESEARCH AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

In this section, the aims and objectives of the research are discussed.

This research is aimed at exploring the possibility of sustainable recycling of plastic waste to create a new industry which promotes a closing of the loop from a waste perspective. Abuja, Nigeria, is being chosen as the urbanistic representation of Nigeria. Firstly, it is the fastest growing city in Nigeria and this explosive growth has resulted in acute house shortage, proliferation of informal

settlements, water scarcity, increased waste production, dilapidated sewer systems and limited resources (Abubakar, 2014; Kadafa et al., 2017; Dumbili and Henderson, 2020). The city's housing shortage is fuelled by immigration and expensive housing caused mostly due to high building costs. There is therefore the need to adopt the use of local building materials and technology to support low-income people to build their homes, especially with the alarming exodus of IDPs into the city from troubled and crisis ridden parts of the country. Amidst its various challenges which is typical for other cities across Nigeria, the Abuja city administration still tries to maintain an elitist vision of a modern and beautiful city and would be willing to explore contributions aimed at solving these challenges (Ayuba et al., 2013; Abubakar, 2014).

The fundamental objectives of the research are:

1. To understand the current situation of plastic use globally and in Nigeria, with a direct focus on its fast-growing capital city, Abuja.
2. To understand the role of various stakeholders in promoting the reuse and recycling of plastic
3. To explore the viability and possibility of adoption of recycled plastic bricks for construction in Abuja and in future, other Nigerian cities
4. This project will promote corporate social responsibility, environmental protection and social inclusion through provision of affordable housing.

1.2.1 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. Why is it imperative that Nigeria develops a sustainable plan towards plastic waste management?
2. What are the techniques involved in the production of plastic bricks?
3. Is there availability of raw materials (recyclable plastic waste) to support a plastic brick factory?
4. Will plastic bricks be acceptable as a replacement for cement bricks for building?
5. Will there be available funding and support by the Federal Government for plastic brick manufacturing?

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This section will provide the data collection and research methodology approach used to address the research questions. Systematic and accurate data collection is critical to scientific research and involves observation, review of documents, measurements, questioning or a combination of the different methods (Kumar, 2015; Abawi, 2017)

For this research, a mixed method approach which is usually reliable and valid and combines both qualitative and quantitative data was adopted. This method develops creative options compared to single design approaches to research and evaluation (Kabir, 2016; Abawi 2017).

The two types of data collection methods engaged for this research were:

1. Interviews for collection of primary data and
2. A desk-based approach that consists of a literature review from journals, publications and recognized websites for secondary data collection.

PRIMARY DATA COLLECTION

The participants recruited for primary data collection were selected because of their expansive experience in recycling, real estate and finance. These are the major stakeholders that would provide qualitative and quantitative data to aid the research conclusions and guide recommendations for further lines of action. The three participants, hereinafter referred to as Respondents 1, 2 and 3, were chosen from personal connections and key informant sampling and are identified as follows:

Respondent 1: Works with a top plastic recycling company located in Abuja. Quantitative and qualitative data was collected on availability and collection of plastic waste raw materials, as well as feasibility of recycling plants and community response to them. Interview transcript is found in Appendix 1

Respondent 2: The Managing Director of a notable real estate company in Abuja, Nigeria. Data is collected to ascertain investor response and possible recommendations as well as acceptability of the product to a building contractor or end-user. Interview transcript is found in Appendix 2.

Respondent 3: The group head, environmental and social risk management of a notable commercial bank in Nigeria: Data collected explored investor response and available financial support from the Bank to a green business. Identifiable financial risks and mitigants were noted. Interview response is found in Appendix 3

SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEW METHOD

Due to the few numbers of respondents recruited, the semi-structured interview (SSI) was adopted- face to face for Respondents 1 and 2, while Respondent 3 was interviewed via semi-structured telephone interview. This was primarily due to the proximity of the respondent to the interviewer. The SSI was chosen to enable open-ended questions and probing for independent thoughts and contributions.

Questions were clarified to respondents and restructured in most cases as well as explanations on answers provided (Adams 2015; Abawi, 2017). As each respondent had a different expertise, questions had same theme but from different lines of interest and points of view.

The respondents were contacted and briefed via telephone calls. Interview dates and venues were also agreed on, and each interview lasted for an average of 45 minutes.

COVID 19 PROTOCOLS DURING INTERVIEWS

To prevent the spread of the corona virus, safety protocols were adopted to lower the risk of spread of the corona virus to and by field personnel during data collection (NBS, 2020). This included use of face masks and temperature checks, social distancing and alcohol-based sanitizers.

There was no physical contact.

Each interview began with pleasantries exchange, followed by a formal disclosure consisting of introduction and presentation of research goals (Nwankpa, 2019). All respondents were given consent sheets to sign off.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION AND CLEARANCE

No sensitive data was sought from respondents. Confidentiality and privacy of all participants were always respected, and a consent form was administered and signed by all respondents as attached in Appendix 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3. The researcher will provide feedback on the research to each respondent and provide a copy of the interview transcript on demand (Nwankpa, 2019).

SECONDARY DATA COLLECTION

Secondary data is data collected from existing resources and was obtained from both quantitative and qualitative research strands. A desk-based approach consisting of literature review from reports, journals and periodicals, publications and browsing reputable online websites was used. The literature review is a critical part of this research as there is currently scant data on recycling and plastic bricks in Abuja. Thus, data was collected from other developing countries and applied to the Nigerian context (Bryman, 2012). Keywords used for the search were: Plastic Waste, Recycling, Waste Management, Abuja, Plastic Brick.

Ethical consideration was minimal, however, only relevant information that will contribute to justify inputs were collected.

LIMITATIONS

Due to the corona virus epidemic, physical interviews were rescheduled multiple times while limited network coverage made it impossible to conduct zoom meetings for some respondents. Identification of relevant stakeholders with efficient knowledge, background or interest in environmental sustainability was challenging hence the limited number of respondents. Recycling companies were not easy to identify and locate.

3.0 EFFECTS OF PLASTIC WASTE

Picture 1: Dead Sea turtle with ingested plastic (Source: Tropical Conservation Fund)

According to the New York Times (2017), over 12 billion metric tons of plastic waste will be accumulated in landfills and the environment by 2050. Shockingly, a report by Simon and Fuhr (2017) has also predicted that by 2050, the weight of plastic waste in the oceans will surpass fish. According to the New York Times, an estimated 5 to 13million metric tons of plastics are accumulated in the oceans annually. Marine animals ingest plastic debris or become entangled in them, resulting in injuries, impaired movement and death. Plastics contain toxic and carcinogenic chemicals in high concentrations and when ingested by bird and marine animals, these chemicals are incorporated in the food chain and are finally consumed by humans (Simon & Fuhr, 2017).

Inadequate management of plastic waste also poses a serious public health and environmental concern (Thompson et al, 2009). Combustion of plastic waste causes release of toxins and GHG

emissions e.g., CO₂ and CO₄, thereby exacerbating climate change (Prata et al., 2021). Combustion and landfilling of plastics waste have also been linked to respiratory disorders caused by release of toxic chemicals such as furans and dioxins.

Plastic litter on land and plastics discarded in landfills leach potentially toxic substances into the soil and water thereby contaminating groundwater, entering the food chain and negatively affecting ecosystems.

COVID 19 PANDEMIC AND SURGE IN PLASTIC USE

Picture 2: Used Covid-19 gloves and disposable masks. Source: The Canadian Press/HO. Regional Municipality of York.

The prediction by Earth Day (2018) that 12 billion plastic wastes discarded in the environment by 2050 will likely be aggravated by the increased demand and use of single use plastics (SUPs) such as gloves and medical masks due to the Covid-19 pandemic (Earth Day, 2018). A report by Silva et al. (2021) has shown a surge in generation of medical waste and plastic packaging due to the pandemic. For instance, on a single day in February 2020, inhabitants of Wuhan, China generated

200 tons of medical plastic waste. Prata et al. (2020) also estimated the monthly use of 65 billion gloves and 129 billion face masks to protect citizens globally.

3.1 GLOBAL PLASTIC WASTE PRODUCTION

By 2050, global population is expected to exceed 9 billion, resulting in increased per capita consumption, resource use and waste generation (Dauvergne, 2010). Over the past decade, municipal solid waste (MSW) generation rates have continued to rise. The World Bank currently predicts a 69% global rise in MSW generation by 2025. This is compared to a baseline annual production rate of 1.3 billion metric tons of waste in 2012 (World Bank Solid Waste Report, 2012).

Figure 1: Breakdown of Individual MSW components in 2018 (USEPA, 2020)

As of 2015, 8.3 billion tons of plastic have been produced, out of which 6.3 billion tons became plastic waste (Earth Day, 2018). Figure 1 shows that plastic solid waste represented 12.2% of 292.4 million tons of waste collected in 2018 (USEPA, 2020). Managing plastic solid waste (PSW) is very expensive, thereby driving several countries and communities to dispose it in open landfill sites. For instance, according to USEPA (2020), Plastics represented 3% of total 112 million tons of waste recycled and composted, leaving 32.6 million tons of plastic to be discarded in 2018 (Table 1). In 2015, 79 percent of PSW globally was disposed in landfills, only 9 percent of plastic waste generated was recycled and 12 percent was incinerated (Chen et al., 2021;).

Table 1: MSW Generation, Recovery and Discard, 2018 (USEPA, 2018)

MSW Component	Weight (per million tonnes)			
	Generated Weight	Recycled/Composting	Combusted	Landfilled
Paper/Paperboard	67.39	45.97	4.20	17.22
Glass	12.25	3.06	1.64	7.55
Metals	25.60	8.72	2.95	13.93
Plastics	35.68	3.09	5.62	26.97
Rubber and Leather	9.16	1.67	2.50	4.99
Textiles	17.03	2.51	3.22	11.30
Wood	18.09	3.10	2.84	12.15
Food	63.13	20.30	7.55	35.28
Yard Trimmings	35.40	22.30	2.57	10.53
Miscellaneous inorganic waste	4.07	0	0.8	3.27
Other materials	4.56	0.97	0.66	2.93
Total Municipal Solid Waste	292.36	111.69	34.55	146.12

Jambeck et al. (2015) estimates that out of 275MMt of plastic waste generated by 195 countries globally, 4.8-12.7 MMt is discarded in the oceans. From 1950 to 2015, 8300 million tonnes (Mt) of plastic was produced globally out of which 76% ended up as waste. 79% of this waste have been discarded in landfills, 12% incinerated and 9% recycled (Babayemi et al, 2019).

Table 2: Top 10 Contributors to Global Plastic Waste Pollution (Jambeck et al., 2015; Earth Day, 2018)

Rank	Country	Generated Waste (kg/ppd)	Plastic Waste (%)	Mismanaged Plastic Waste (MMT/annum)
1	China	1.10	11	8.82
2	Indonesia	0.52	11	3.22
3	Philippines	0.5	15	1.88
4	Vietnam	0.79	13	1.83
5	Sri Lanka	5.1	7	1.59
6	Thailand	1.2	12	1.03
7	Egypt	1.37	13	0.97
8	Malaysia	1.52	13	0.94
9	Nigeria	0.79	13	0.85
10	Bangladesh	0.43	8	0.79

MMT- Million Metric Tons; ppd- Persons per day

3.1.2. PLASTIC CONSUMPTION AND WASTE IN AFRICA

As population grows, and urbanization spreads, consumer patterns have changed leading to an exponential growth in waste generation. According to a report by Godfrey et al. (2019), an estimated 13% of MSW generated in Africa is plastic waste. Between 1990 and 2017, an estimated 172Mt of plastics and polymers, valued at \$285 billion were imported by 54 African countries (Babayemi et al., 2019). Six countries (Figure 2) account for 230Mt (75%) of imported plastics between 1990 and 2017. (Babayemi et al, 2019; HBS, 2020).

Figure 2: Top 6 Importers and consumers of Plastic in Africa (Babayemi et al, 2019)

Total plastic production in eight countries between 2009 and 2015 was 15.9Mt, with the highest productions being from South Africa (9.0Mt), Egypt (4.0Mt) and Nigeria (2.3Mt) (Babayemi et al, 2019)

3.1.3 NIGERIA: PLASTIC USE AND WASTE GENERATION

In Nigeria, 25Mt of municipal solid waste are generated annually. Between 2000 and 2017, the population growth of Nigeria averaged at 2.37% and directly resulted to increased MSW and by extension, plastic wastes generation (Duru et al., 2019). Table 3 shows different waste generation rates across major cities in Nigeria. According to the report by Jambeck et al. (2015), with a recorded 0.85 MMt of plastic waste being mismanaged, Nigeria is the 9th highest contributor to plastic waste in the world. Over 20 million tons of plastic was imported into Nigeria between 1996 and 2017, making Nigeria the 2nd largest importer of plastic in the continent (HBS, 2020; Babayemi et al., 2019). (Table 2).

Table 3: MSW generation for different cities in Nigeria (Ayuba et al., 2013)

CITY	Tonnage per month	Density (Kg/m ³)	Kg/capital/day
Lagos	255,556	294	0.63
Kano	156,676	290	0.56
Ibadan	135,391	330	0.51
Kaduna	114,433	320	0.58
Port-Harcourt	117,825	300	0.60
Makurdi	24,242	340	0.48
Onitsha	84,137	310	0.53
Nsukka	12,000	370	0.44.
Abuja	14,785	280	0.66

Between 2010 and 2015, over 2.1 million tons of plastic waste was produced in Nigeria (Tiseo, 2021). Most of the plastic waste produced in Nigeria are mis-managed, thus majority of PSW are incinerated or dumped on the street, drainages or in the water ways. Three rivers from Nigeria-Cross, Imo and Kira Ibo rivers are among the top twenty most polluted rivers in the world, contributing 67% of global plastic inflows into the oceans (Lebreton et al, 2017).

Picture 3: Streets overtaken by waste after heavy rainfall in Lagos. Source : Ilo, 2020

The Nigerian government has failed to provide basic amenities to support population growth thereby exacerbating plastic pollution. For example, the non-provision of safe drinking water by the government has resulted in the use of plastic packaged table water (sachet water) as a means of ameliorating water shortage (Dumbili and Henderson, 2020). According to Edoga et al. (2017), 70% of Nigerians use and dispose 60 million plastic sachets daily. Due to improper disposal, these plastic sachets litter Nigerian streets, lay waste on soil, block drainages and cause wildfires, flood and breeding of mosquitoes and other pests. A recent boat accident in Port-Harcourt, Nigeria was caused by plastic waste which got entangled with the propeller blades of the boat (Duru et al,2019).

Picture 5: PET bottles blocking a drainage in Lagos State, Nigeria. Source: The Guardian News (2015)

3.2. CASE STUDY: ABUJA, NIGERIA: GEOGRAPHICAL BACKGROUND

Abuja, the capital of Nigeria, is a city located north of the confluence of the Benue and Niger Rivers, at an elevation of 2760 ft above sea-level, at latitude 9.07N and longitude 7.48E(Abubakar, 2014). Abuja has a land mass of 7,315sq km and is famous for its mild weather due to its tropical location and elevation (Encyclopedia Britanica, 2021). It has 6 local area councils: Abuja municipal, Abaji, Bwari, Kuje, Gwagwalada and Kwali (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Map of Abuja, Nigeria (Oladimeji et al., 2017)

The city is headed by an appointed minister and is run by the Federal Capital Territory Administration (FCTA). The FCTA has various arms such as the Abuja Water Board (AWB), Abuja Geographical Information System (AGIS), Abuja Environmental Protection Board (AEPB) amongst others, all headed by directors.

Figure 4: Map showing different districts in Abuja, Nigeria. (Oladimeji et al., 2017)

3.2.1 CHALLENGES FACED IN ABUJA

Like many developing cities, Abuja is experiencing an astronomical boom in population growth with an urbanization rate of 8.32% and a population size of 1.4million as of 2006, and projected population of 3,564,100 as at 2016 (Myers, 2011; City Population, 2020; Encyclopedia Britannica, 2021). This population growth has been attributed to massive immigration people in search of jobs, safety and better economic opportunities. This has however resulted in housing issues, proliferation of slum settlements, water scarcity and inefficient sanitation and waste management facilities (Abubakar, 2014; Salami et al., 2019). The Abuja masterplan is meant to epitomize a

modern master-city; however, the city has become characterized as socially exclusive with the city center populated by the elite while the suburbs are heavily populated and lacking in infrastructure.

HOUSING IN ABUJA, NIGERIA

The housing deficit in Abuja is further fueled by massive immigration including scores of Nigerians fleeing the conflict-ridden North-East to Abuja daily. Peace Foundation (2020) estimates the current IDPS population in Abuja at 21,000. Most of the IDPs live in shelters built from make-shift tents, corrugated iron sheets, plywood and plastic sheets because their host communities lack the resources to support them (Peace Foundation, 2020; Desai, 2018).

Picture 7: Makeshift Shelters for IDPs in Durumi Camp, Abuja. Source: Desai, 2018

Rising costs of building materials also contributes to the lack of affordable housing. Sandcrete blocks made from cement, sand and water are extensively used for the construction of houses and infrastructure in the city and the cost of cement, which is the predominant material used in brick/block manufacturing is increasing with rising demands (Sholanke et al., 2015). Between 1999 and 2002, the cost of cement increased by 300%, maintained a 23% growth rate till 2008 and then increased by 35% in 2020 due to high production costs, low production rates, increased transport cost and the corona virus pandemic (Adewole, 2008; Perilli, 2021). Increased cement price has also resulted in production of substandard bricks by producers who use wrong mix ratios in order to meet up with high demand. These substandard bricks break during transportation, are unable to

stand seismic activity and pose grave danger to a structure if used as load bearing walls (Sholanke et al., 2015).

3.2.2 WASTE GENERATION, COMPOSITION AND MANAGEMENT IN ABUJA.

According to Imam et al. (2007), the Abuja Environmental Protection Board (AEPB) disposes and collects waste in the FCT. A report by ACCP (2019) shows that 1,192 tons of waste is generated daily (0.42kg/person/day) in Abuja. The waste generated is heterogenous with the main components being organic waste, plastics, paper, glass and metals (Table 2). Waste is collected 2-3 times weekly by 12 private firms in Abuja. The only sorting or recycling done is by informal sector workers or scavengers who collect materials for recycling before waste is being transported to the landfill.

Picture 6: Inefficient waste collection in Gwarimpa, Abuja (Source: Researcher)

Waste collected is disposed of in open dumps or the single unsanitary landfill located in Mpape Abuja. This dumpsite is characterized by unsavory stench, air pollution from burning and indiscriminate ground dumping, without any groundwater protection, treatment or leachate recovery (Salami et al., 2019; Ayuba et al., 2013)

3.2.3 PLASTIC WASTE GENERATION IN ABUJA

Plastic waste ranked second after food remnants in the food waste composition data provided for Abuja by various researchers. Table 2 shows an ACCP (2019) report where plastic waste represents 15% of all waste collected in Abuja, second only to food waste which is 43%. The packaging sector is one of the major consumers of plastics as it is used extensively for food production, wrapper cellophane and drinking/ beverage bottles (Kadafa et al., 2017). Consequently, in Abuja, increased plastic waste generation is due to the high earning capacity and lifestyle of Abuja dwellers. However, the slums equally consume very high amounts of plastic which are not effectively managed or disposed of.

Table 4. Heterogenous Components of MSW in Abuja (%net weight) (Source: ACCP, 2019)

S/N	MATERIAL	GENERATION (% Net Weight)
1	Food Remnant	43.43
2	Plastic Waste	15.27
3	Paper	7.76
4	Textile	1.39
5	Wood	3.36
6	Rubber & Leather	0.08
7	Metals	2.02
8	Glass	2.39
9	Others (soils, ceramics etc.)	24.18

Another report by Imam et al. (2008) which compared the components of MSW generated in all the six districts of Abuja Federal Capital City (FCC) showed that the only waste type higher than plastic was food waste. According to Kadafa et al. (2017), six major types of plastic mostly thermoplastics, have been isolated from MSW in Abuja (Table 5) and Duru et al (2019) cited the use of sachet water and polyethylene bag as one of the major reasons for high prevalence of the plastic waste in MSW.

Table 5: Common Plastic Components of MSW found in Abuja (Kadafa et al., 2017; Duru et al,2019;)

S/N	PLASTIC TYPE	PRODUCT EXAMPLE
1	Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET)	Soft drink bottles, video tape, X-ray film
2	High Density Polyethylene (HDPE)	Detergent bottles, milk cans, pipes, toys
3	Low Density Polyethylene (LDPE)	Clingfilm, playground slides
4	Polyvinyl Chloride (PVC)	Electric wire insulation, Pipes, shoes, automotive, flooring, plumbing
5	Polypropylene (PP)	Hinges, Furniture, toys, tubing
6	Polystyrene (PS)	Insulation, CD Cases, Foam protection

3.3 PLASTIC WASTE MANAGEMENT

According to Dayrit (2019) and Duru et al. (2019), a holistic approach which incorporates functions and lifecycle should be adopted with regards to plastic waste management. This approach will enable waste plastic recovery in a close looped cycle and include all stakeholders, from industry to consumers and the government. They proposed the 5Rs approach to waste management (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle, Recover and Discard) and identified recycling as the most viable and resourceful approach to plastic waste management.

Fig 5 : Management of Plastic Waste (Duru et al., 2019)

RECYCLING IN ABUJA

Only 9% of plastic waste is recycled globally, while in Nigeria, less than 12% of all plastic collected is recycled (Babayemi et al, 2019; Keyinde et al., 2020). Nigeria has eight recycling plants which are mostly located in the cities of Lagos, Onitsha, Aba, Abuja and Kano (Magoum, 2021; Duru et al., 2019). These plants engage in secondary recycling methods and if all plastic recyclables were recovered, they have capacities to recycle less than 30%. This is unlike countries like Germany that recycles and composts 65% of their MSW and Lithuania, Bulgaria and India that recycles 69%, 59% and 50% of their plastic waste respectively (OECD, 2015; Duru et al., 2019, Eurostat, 2021)

According to a report by ACCP (2019), less than 3% of all waste generated in Abuja is recycled. There is no formal recycling program, consequently, recycling is usually carried out by the private sector, with collection and sorting by the informal sector and scavengers. 45% of waste generated is disposed at landfills while 52% are disposed at generation sources and litter the streets (Verma et al., 2016; Olanrewaju and Oyebade, 2019).

3.3.1 BENEFITS OF RECYCLING

Recycling is recognized as a driving force for socio-economic development due to its effects on the environment and economy. According to Kehinde et al. (2020), the economic advantages of plastic recycling are derived from energy conservation, GHG emissions reduction, protection of non-renewable oil and gas resources (used for plastic production) and improvement of livelihoods through the creation of white collar and informal jobs.). Plastic recycling will reduce the burden of sourcing foreign exchange for the importation of raw materials and virgin resin, for example, between 1996 and 2017, Nigeria imported plastics valued at \$23.1billion (Olanrewaju and Oyebade, 2019; Babayemi et al., 2019). Recycling also reduces resource use and funds used to address drainage challenges, landfills clearing, management and ocean cleanup and reduces the waste on landfills and oceans. Plastic waste can be converted into energy through waste to energy processes and used to form composite materials in agriculture, fashion (e.g., polyester) and construction. (Olanrewaju and Oyebade, 2019; Kehinde et al., 2020).

RECYCLED PLASTIC IN CONSTRUCTION

Plastic waste can be crushed and used as additives in construction mixtures (e.g., tiles and cement) to increase porosity and the mechanical and physical strength of the material (Kehinde et al., 2019). Recycled plastic waste can replace traditional sand and gravel used in asphalt or molded into plugs for portholes as used in countries such as India (NLR, 2020). Plastic bottles can be filled with sand and used to form Eco bricks for building as seen in Yelwa, Nigeria, where PET bottles were filled with sand and used to build homes (Haque, 2019; NLR, 2020).

3.3.2 WHAT IS PLASTIC BRICK?

Plastic Bricks by Start-up- Conceptos Plasticos for School Classrooms in Kenya (Source: Neira, 2021)

Plastic can be melted, molded or incorporated with sand to form plastic bricks for building homes and roads. Agrawal et al. (2017) manufactured plastic bricks from a mix of 70% recycled PET bottles, laterite soil and 2% bitumen. The PET bottles were melted at 260°C and mixed with laterite sand and bitumen as the binding agent, poured into molds and compacted. The bricks were demolded after 15 minutes and left to air-dry for 24 hours. Indrajeet et al. (2018) investigated the properties of plastic bricks by crushing LDPE into pellets which were subsequently melted at 400°C in an injection molding machine, then poured and left to cool, forming plastic bricks (Table 6). The resultant plastic bricks by the two researchers showed no water absorption, nil efflorescence and higher compressive strength when compared to standard bricks.

Table 6. Compressive strength of plastic bricks compared to standard cement bricks (Indrajeet et al., 2018)

S/No	LOAD AT FAILURE (KN)		COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH(N/mm ²)	
	PLASTIC BRICK	STANDARD BRICK	PLASTIC BRICK	STANDARD BRICK
1	730	451	46.62	26.42

2	525	310	30.68	22.78
3	486	350	28.46	20.46

Kamble and Karad (2017) compared properties of standard bricks with plastic brick samples from molten plastic, sand and coal tar, concluding that the compressive strength of plastic bricks is 2700kgf/cm² with moisture content of 0.74%, which is satisfactory when compared to standard cement bricks (Table 7). Plastic bricks are durable, waterproof, heat and cold resistant and cheap. Haque (2019) conducted a cost comparison within the context of Bangladesh as shown in Table 7, concluding that plastic brick wall is 54% cheaper than cement wall. Plastic bricks can also withstand seismic activity, are eco-friendly and are particularly efficient in conflict areas because of their bullet-proof properties. (Agrawal et al., 2017, Indrajeet et al, 2018; Haque, 2019; Kumar et al., 2021)

Table 7: Comparison of Plastic Brick and Normal Cement brick (Kamble and Karad, 2017; Haque, 2019; Haque and Islam, 2021)

Type of Brick	Weight (g)	% Water Absorption	% Moisture Content	Strength of Material (N/mm ²)	Interior Temperature	Cost (BDT)
Normal Brick	1800	3.94	0.55	8.58	29°C- 34°C	16,837.58
Plastic Brick	1070	0.92	0.74	34.69	18°C	7,733.42

In addressing the solution for housing deficit, the Nigerian government, in 2004, established a plan to provide 8 million new homes and adopted the utilization of waste plastic bottles to provide homes as shown in Yelwa (Pati et al., 2014; Mokhtar et al., 2016)

Picture 9: Plastic Brick House by Conceptos Plasticos. Source: Neira, 2021)

In Columbia, a start-up company, Conceptos Plasticos transformed plastic residues and rubber into lego-like blocks which are used for construction of homes (Foggin, 2018; Neira, 2021). So far, they have recycled 200tons of plastic waste to build homes for 42 families displaced by violence in Guapi, Cauca and partnered with UNICEF providing low-cost plastic brick classrooms in Côte d’ivoire (Foggin, 2018; Valencia, 2017). In 5 days and at a cost of \$6,800 and 5 labourers, they built a two-bedroom, confirming cheap labour and material (Valencia, 2017).

4.0 RESULTS

This section discusses data collected from the respondents that were interviewed. The current waste collection cycle in Abuja is that scavengers rummage roadside dumps and waste collection receptacles, collecting a monthly average of 200 tons of waste across Chanja Daiti hubs in Abuja. Waste is also collected from volunteer organizations such as embassies, schools and factories while individuals drop off their used plastics for a fee. The waste is subsequently transported for sorting, cleaning and preparation for recycling. Polypropylene plastic is sorted and crushed into pellets then sold to local manufacturers for re-production. Sorted PET bottles and containers are

sold and transported to Lagos, Nigeria, where there is demand. Costs incurred in the recycling plant are mostly on land, power and transportation. Payments to suppliers range from N20-N40 depending on location. Chanja Daiti has introduced various initiatives such as 'Bottles for Books Program' which monetized donated waste to send out of school children back to school. It had positive community response while another program- 'Recycredits' which allows suppliers earn points which can be later redeemed was not widely accepted because people want instant gratifications. Demand for recycled pellets is more than supply because of low numbers of recycling plants, inefficient power supply which slows down recycling process, lack of funding and lack of awareness on benefits of recycling. Although the recycling business is slow in Abuja, passion and patience drives the business because profits are slim.

Data from the Chief Executive Officer of a top real estate company, Wallhouse West-Africa Ltd indicates that the housing deficit in Abuja has worsened since the Covid-19 pandemic, with a 20% slump in home sales. This is partly caused by the lack of mortgage programs which foster affordable housing, as well as the rising cost of construction materials such as cement. The most common material used for building are blocks made from a mixture of cement and sand. Prices of blocks differ depending on the quality and strength of the blocks; however, the average cost of a block is N200-N250. Table 8 represents the cost of building a 2- bedroom building with cement blocks in Abuja:

Table 8: Building cost of 2-bedroom home with standard bricks

TOTAL COST OF BUILDING	BLOCK COMPONENT	AMOUNT	PERIOD
N10,500,000/\$25,666.10	40%	N4,500,000/\$10,999.76	90 days

Rates: N409.1/\$1 (CBN, 2021)

In the company's environmental and sustainability transition plan, they are willing to explore ways to reduce their carbon footprint. While they are not averse to the use of plastic bricks, the following concerns were raised:

1. Attraction of plastic bricks for a builder or homeowner would depend on the cost-effectiveness of the product.
2. Solar irradiation in Abuja is very high so there is need to investigate the durability and effect of high temperatures on the plastic bricks and thus, the feasibility of its adoption.
3. Adopting plastic bricks as a social housing scheme but will require funding and interventions such as awareness programs and government rewards for implementation.

Data collected from the third respondent indicated that commercial banks are adopting processes and developing people to manage their GHG emissions and reduce their carbon footprint due to Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN)'s policy on Nigerian Sustainable Banking Principles. Customers are being encouraged to green their businesses while staff and processes are being reevaluated to become more environmentally sustainable. These include portfolio greening policies such as cutting down fossil-fuel use and issuance of green financial instruments such as the green bonds e.g. as issued by Access Bank Plc in 2018. These Climate bond instruments manage Climate change, promote physical and economic development, and employment. Renewal energy systems such as solar energy are also being supported through funding while green champions are appointed to manage, monitor and report activities which exacerbate climate change, while recommending mitigative actions. While funding initiatives exist for the renewal energy industry, they however, identified knowledge gap and technology as major barriers to entrepreneurial adoption of such sustainable projects. They also cited sustainability principles need to be practicalized across banks while Nigerian government needs policy shifts to aggressively tackle climate change. Although recycling may be a new sector for Banks, it is a fundable venture which will yield economic and environmental benefits, thereby placing Nigeria to achieve its climate change mitigation goals.

All the respondents unanimously agreed that while plastic waste is an abundant and sustainable raw material, a lot of awareness and sensitization is needed on the debilitating effects of plastic waste as well as the benefits of recycling and a sustainable lifestyle.

5.0 DISCUSSION

This section critically analyses, discusses and aggregates the key results for use in the conclusion and recommendation of the study.

As highlighted in chapter 3, plastic waste is an issue of great concern globally and in Nigeria, increased population growth, poverty and poor waste management practices have exacerbated the plastic waste scourge. The focus for this research is Abuja, the capital city of Nigeria which is representative of the core environmental and social issues in Nigerian cities. Abuja is one of the fastest growing cities in the world, and with population growth and a high urbanization rate of 8.3%, it faces a mirage of challenges such as proliferation of slum settlements, water scarcity and inefficient sanitation and waste management facilities (Myers, 2011; Abubakar, 2014). Plastic waste is second to organic waste in the MSW composition of Abuja (Imam et al., 2007; ACCP, 2019). However, there is no government intervention in the plastic waste management process. Recycling is inefficient due to lack of available technology and high operating and recycling costs, with power identified as a major barrier. Although 15% of all plastic waste generated in Abuja is plastic, results show limited availability of recyclable plastic materials (Imam, 2008; Kadafa et al., 2017; ACCP, 2019). This could be attributed to lack of standard plastic waste collection and sorting programs, existence of few recycling plants. These factors have resulted in discarding of plastic waste in landfills and water bodies such as lakes and rivers thereby contaminating surface water, causing soil infertility and adversely affecting aquatic and terrestrial life (Thompson et al., 2009; Verma et al., 2016; Simon and Fuhr, 2017). In addition, Abuja has an open dumping trend which causes visual intrusion, air pollution and emission of greenhouse gases which adversely affects human health and leads to global warming (Duru et al., 2019; Dumbili and Henderson, 2020).

Plastic waste as a replacement for cement will decrease GHG emissions, as 8% of global CO₂ emissions are from the thermal and chemical processes in cement production (Chatham House, 2018; Rogers, 2018; Mohamad et al., 2021). Plastic bricks also reduce the number of plastics being incinerated or entering oceans and landfill. Bhushariah et al. (2017) has countered that burning of plastic for preparation of plastic brick emits noxious gases into the environment. However, Agrawal et al (2017) and Kumar et al. (2021) have identified PET as a viable material for plastic

brick production and having atomic composition of carbon, hydrogen and oxygen, will not generate GHG gases when combusted. Our results show PET is sustainable as raw-material plastic waste in Abuja because it has no recycling demand.

Plastic bricks as a replacement for cement will reduce the cost of housing and provide a means of shelter especially for IDPs. Review of literature has shown that plastic bricks are more economical than standard cement bricks. Haque (2019) showed that standard masonry bricks are 54% higher in cost than plastic brick (Table 7). Literature showed material cost of a 2bedroom house with regular cement bricks as \$10,999.76 while our result showed a cost of \$6,800, thereby confirming that plastic bricks are 38% more cost effective than cement bricks.

Research has shown that plastic brick is more durable and has 4x more compressive strength than standard cement bricks (Table 7). Plastic bricks are also thermo-acoustic, water and fire-proof, and can withstand high temperatures. In Yelwa, Nigeria, PET bottles have been used to build bullet proof homes, also confirming the feasibility of plastic brick use in Nigeria despite the hot climate.. Available research concludes that plastic waste is abundantly available, and is durable in terms of strength, weight and absorption when compared to standard cement bricks (Kumar et al., 2021). Since high cement prices continue to increase, alternatives such as plastic bricks will be very desirable as a stimulant for socio-economic development in Abuja.

In 2004, the Nigerian government, in a bid to provide of 8 million homes, explored the possibility of plastic brick use (Mokhtar, 2016; Haque, 2021). By implications, they will support plastic brick projects given their eco-conservative, economical and socio-economic advantages. Following the mandate by commercial banks to reduce their carbon footprint and support green businesses, they will be willing and able to support plastic brick industry. Plastic bricks are a novel product which sets Nigeria on a Paris-compliant GHG reduction pathway and will provide affordable housing especially for internally displaced citizens.

6.0 CONCLUSION

This research shows that adoption of plastic bricks as a construction material in Abuja is an environmentally sustainable and feasible way of mitigating effects of plastic waste pollution because it reduces GHG emissions from plastic waste burning, land filling and cement production.

Plastic bricks are also affordable and durable, thus it will promote socioeconomical growth through employment and cheap housing. There is a wealth of research that shows that with adequate sensitization and funding, plastic brick manufacturing can be effectively adopted in Abuja and subsequently, other Nigerian cities. However, all relevant stakeholders- individuals, organizations, recycling companies, financial institutions, government and international organizations, should be engaged and with the following lines of action adopted:

1. Aggressive sensitization of all relevant stakeholders on the effects of plastic waste and benefits of plastic recycling for production of plastic bricks
2. Funding interventions and grants from government, mortgage/commercial banks, private or international organizations for establishment of a solar-powered plastic-brick manufacturing plant.
3. An incentive program to promote the cleaning, sorting and collection of plastic waste from source.
4. Advanced research on the effect of variation of plastic content and climate type on the compressive strength and properties of plastic bricks used in Nigeria.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1 – Interview Transcript: Respondent 1

Interviewer: Can you introduce yourself?

Respondent 1: My name is Chukwu Alex, and I will be in this interview representing the M.D of Chanja Datti Recycling Company. Chanja Datti is a recycling company situated in Abuja, Durumi, precisely.

Interviewer: Firstly, what is Chanja Datti and what is your role in the organization?

Respondent 1: Chanja Datti is a recycling company, actually the acronym is Hausa Language, meaning transforming waste to value. I am the inventory manager.

Interviewer: Could you explain what is a complete waste collection cycle, from waste collection to manufacturing of your end products?

Respondent 1: Let me start by saying that Chanja Datti has been in existence for more than 5 years. Over this time, we have developed various methods of collecting waste. For example, in our head office in Area 1, you can look around and see lots of PET bottles. These boys (scavengers) stay here in the factory and go and pick recyclables, they bring them here, we weigh and pay immediately. Also, different organizations such as Red cross, Jaiz, Shoprite outlets and embassies, we pick up their waste. However, we only collect recyclables such as paper, metal, metal scraps and plastics, we do not collect organic waste. We sort by ourselves, there are workers that sort at the factory.

Interviewer: How do you develop and manage your network of plastic waste suppliers?

Respondent 1: Like what I said earlier, we have the data of all our boys. Most of them do not know banking so we open bank accounts for them. They bring the waste, and we make money transfers to their accounts.

Interviewer: What is the payment rate for your suppliers, and how are they paid?

Respondent 1: Actually, price fluctuates so we are not in charge of the price. Area 1 is N20 per Kilo while Giri is N40 per Kilo, all due to transport.

Interviewer: What is the frequency, volume and pattern of waste collected weekly?

Respondent 1: The boys go out twice- morning and night. Ten of them can give 10tonnes, while organizations, we go to collect on Mondays, Wednesdays and some Fridays. Across the hubs, 200tonnes are collected in a month.

Interviewer: How is waste sorted before being transported to the factory?

Respondent 1: Here we don't do a lot of sorting, we transport them to Giri where we have over 50 women that sort the bottles, remove the labels and caps and get it ready for recycling.

Interviewer: How do your scrap pickers transport waste to the factory?

Respondent 1: We have about 4 trucks and 1 compactor. Bringing the waste is not a problem. We recycle only the covers. The PET bottles are sent to Lagos.

Interviewer: Is there a particular type of plastic that is used for the pellets?

Respondent 1: We recycle plastic nylon, not PEP. We remove the covers which is Polypropylene-PP, which is transported to Lagos where the facilities and demand exists. After sorting, we wash, sieve and dry the plastic before crushing in the machine into pellets. Local manufacturers then buy the pellets which they use to produce new products.

Interviewer: What is the by-product of the recycling process?

Respondent 1: We try to us up everything as we are trying to reduce waste, not produce it.

Interviewer: How do you dispose of the by-products?

Respondent 1: Refer to above answer

Interviewer: Who are the buyers of your end products?

Respondent 1: There are a lot of off-takers who use our products to re-manufacture things. For instance, you can recycle a broken plastic chair to a bucket. We actually are not able to meet demands despite available raw materials.

Interviewer: Could you explain what the initiative 'Bottles for Books' is?

Respondent 1: In Chanja Datti, there are a lot of programs. In bottles for Books, individuals donate waste which are monetized and used to bring out of school children back to school.

Interviewer: Could you explain what is the initiative 'Recycredits' all about, and how does it work?

Respondent 1: Recycredits was developed when we started newly. You earn a point when you bring in recyclables and the point is redeemed later. However, people did not buy this idea because they want immediate payment.

Interviewer: How has the community responded to these products?

Respondent 1: Bottles for Books has far more reception than Recycredits as explained earlier. A lot of institutions like Regent School, American International College, American Embassy and other individuals have been bringing in waste for this program. We always give appreciation certificates.

Interviewer: What major challenges have you faced recently?

Respondent 1: Everyone in Nigeria knows what the problem is- Power. Once the lights (power) go out, machines shut down completely and work stops. Like here, we do not have a generator. Funds will be needed for an alternative source of power and better machinery.

Interviewer: Having been in business for 6 years, would you encourage recycling as a business to a prospective entrepreneur?

Respondent 1: I will be frank, a lot of people come around, but there are things you do in this business to succeed or fail. Materials are available, off-takers that can buy are here, but you need funding first, and then passion and resilience to succeed in this. This business is profitable in the long run. You must give it some time.

Interviewer: Is there anything else you would like to add?

Respondent 1: You really need secured space for waste. People need to know more about waste and how to make money. You also need passion to excel. Thank you.

APPENDIX 1.1 PARTICIPANT AGREEMENT FORM – RESPONDENT 1

Participant Agreement Form

The title of the research project

Promoting a circular economy through plastic recycling. What is the feasibility and environmental impact of using plastic recycled products for building in Abuja, Nigeria?

Name, position and contact details of researcher

Ugochi Emeka-okanu, Graduate Green Economy Student at Bournemouth University
Contact at – ugookanu@gmail.com

Name, position and contact details of supervisor

Tilak Ginige, Senior Lecturer in Environmental Law
Contact at – tginige@bournemouth.ac.uk

To be completed prior to data collection activity

Section A: Agreement to participate in the study

You should only agree to participate in the study if you agree with all of the statements in this table and accept that participating will involve the listed activities.

<p>I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet and have been given access to the BU Research Participant Privacy Notice which sets out how we collect and use personal information (https://www1.bournemouth.ac.uk/about/governance/access-information/data-protection-privacy).</p>
<p>I have had the opportunity to ask questions.</p>
<p>I understand that my participation is voluntary. I can stop participating in research activities at any time without giving a reason and I am free to decline to answer any question(s).</p>
<p>I understand that taking part in the research will include the following activities as part of the research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being audio recorded during the interview • My words will be quoted in publications, reports, web pages or other research outputs using my real name
<p>I understand that, if I withdraw from the study, I will also be able to withdraw my data from further use in the study except where my data has been anonymised (as I cannot be identified) or it will be harmful to the project to have my data removed</p>
<p>I understand that my data may be included in an anonymised form within a dataset to be archived at BU's Online Research Data Repository</p>

I understand that my data may be used in an anonymised form by the research team to support other research projects in the future, including future publications, reports or presentations	
Initial box to agree	
I consent to take part in the project on the basis set out above (Section A)	

I confirm my agreement to take part in the project on the basis set out above.

<u>Chukwu Alex</u> Name of participant (BLOCK CAPITALS)	<u>15/04/2021</u> Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	<u>[Signature]</u> Signature
<u>UGOCHI EMEKA-OKANU</u> Name of researcher (BLOCK CAPITALS)	<u>15/04/2021</u> Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	<u>[Signature]</u> Signature

Appendix 2 – Interview Transcript: Respondent 2

Interviewer: How long have you been in real estate, and what is your role in Wallhouse West Africa Ltd?

Respondent 2: Let me start by saying, my name is Chuka Odom, I am the Chairman/CEO of Wallhouse West Africa Ltd. Wallhouse is a real estate company incorporated under the laws of Nigeria in 1990. We have been in business for more than 20 years. My role comprises policy direction, project conception, budgeting, implementation and general administration.

Interviewer: How many homes do you build in a year?

Respondent 2: In the past year, we have done 60 units of 2-bedroom, 3 -bedroom and terrace apartments in two locations- Abuja and Lagos.

Interviewer: How many homes do you sell on an average in a year?

Respondent 2: We sell at least 40-45% of all constructed homes but in the past 18months, we have noticed a 20% slump in home purchase due to the Covid 19 pandemic. In addition, the naira took a plunge and this has affected building materials by at least 25% in the last 12 months. Most importantly, the lull in home purchase is from poor earnings as the mortgage platform in Nigeria is very weak and 70-75% of home purchase is on cash and carry basis.

Interviewer: What type of materials do you use for walls/frames?

Respondent 2: Essentially, we use cement blocks for walls and partitioning and wood for frames.

Interviewer: Currently, what are the bricks that you use made of?

Respondent 2: The bricks are made from a mixture of cement, sand and water which are either hand molded or machine molded to form blocks. Cement is accessed basically through 2 companies- BUA and Dangote cement who have monopolized the market and control prices. Sand is gotten from water canals across the country.

Interviewer: How do you source for bricks on-site?

Respondent 2: There are 2 ways of sourcing for bricks. The developer can mold by themselves to ensure an appropriate mix, or more commonly, can buy from roadside block manufacturers. Depending on the quality, the price varies.

Interviewer: How much on average does a brick cost?

Respondent 2: Blocks come in different sizes and prices. The most common are 9inch and 6inch blocks. Right now, they sell between N180-N250 respectively.

Interviewer: Can you estimate how much and how long it would take to build a 40-square, 2-bedroom house?

Respondent 2: A 40-square, 2-bedroom house with 1 living room, 1 kitchen, 1 dining and a toilet will cost about N10.5million, with the brick component representing 40% of this amount. Depending on the availability of materials and preparedness of a developer, it will approximately take 90days to build.

Interviewer: What environmental management activities do you engage in presently or are you hoping to engage in the future?

Respondent 2: The environmental impact assessment on any project site is dependent on the site and location of the property. We encourage environment friendly buildings through greenery, and open spaces to reduce brick component. We also encourage use of solar power against fossil fuel use for power generation. It is a policy that location e.g. high traffic, guides our decisions in reducing our carbon footprint. We are also open to new ideas that help us explore energy efficient systems.

Interviewer: What factors would make you interested in integrating recycled plastic products as part of your construction materials?

Respondent 2: Cost component. Ofcourse, the prices of the bricks as against standard blocks must be considered. Then there must be adequate research on the quality of plastic brick and its strength in the Nigerian climate. We also need sensitization for consumers and support from Nigerian government.

Interviewer: Is there anything else you would like to add?

Respondent 2: We need a viable mortgage platform to solve the housing deficit in Abuja. There is expected huge investments to deliver infrastructure and housing needs. Thank you.

APPENDIX 2.1 PARTICIPANT AGREEMENT FORM – RESPONDENT 2

Participant Agreement Form

The title of the research project
 Promoting a circular economy through plastic recycling. What is the feasibility and environmental impact of using plastic recycled products for building in Abuja, Nigeria?

Name, position and contact details of researcher
 Ugochi Emeka-okanu, Graduate Green Economy Student at Bournemouth University
 Contact at – ugookanu@gmail.com

Name, position and contact details of supervisor
 Tilak Ginige, Senior Lecturer in Environmental Law
 Contact at – tginige@bournemouth.ac.uk

To be completed prior to data collection activity

Section A: Agreement to participate in the study

You should only agree to participate in the study if you agree with all of the statements in this table and accept that participating will involve the listed activities.

<p>I have read and understood the Participant Information Sheet and have been given access to the BU Research Participant Privacy Notice which sets out how we collect and use personal information (https://www.bournemouth.ac.uk/about/governance/access-information/data-protection-privacy).</p>
<p>I have had the opportunity to ask questions.</p>
<p>I understand that my participation is voluntary. I can stop participating in research activities at any time without giving a reason and I am free to decline to answer any question(s).</p>
<p>I understand that taking part in the research will include the following activities as part of the research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being audio recorded during the interview • My words will be quoted in publications, reports, web pages or other research outputs using my real name
<p>I understand that, if I withdraw from the study, I will also be able to withdraw my data from further use in the study except where my data has been anonymised (as I cannot be identified) or it will be harmful to the project to have my data removed</p>
<p>I understand that my data may be included in an anonymised form within a dataset to be archived at BU's Online Research Data Repository</p>

I understand that my data may be used in an anonymised form by the research team to support other research projects in the future, including future publications, reports or presentations	
Initial box to agree	
I consent to take part in the project on the basis set out above (Section A)	

I confirm my agreement to take part in the project on the basis set out above.

<u>Chika Odum</u> Name of participant (BLOCK CAPITALS)	<u>10/4/21</u> Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	<u></u> Signature
<u>UGOCHI EMEKA-OKANU</u> Name of researcher (BLOCK CAPITALS)	<u>10/04/2021</u> Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	<u></u> Signature

Appendix 3 – Interview Transcript: Respondent 3

Interviewer: Can you introduce yourself?

Respondent 3: My name is Gbenga Adeleke, and I am the Group head, environmental and social risk management, Access Bank, Nigeria. We currently have 15 subsidiaries some of which are in South Africa, Kenya, Ghana, Mozambique and UAE.

Interviewer: Which Green Banking/Climate Initiatives has your institution put in place?

Respondent: For more than 10 years, Access Bank has focused on greening the economy. In September 2012, the Central Bank of Nigeria developed its policy on Nigerian sustainability banking principles which guided Banks to make contributions to climate change mitigation. Access Bank has adopted its policy on people and process. So far, we have 15 professional staff on climate change management and green champions that monitor, evaluate, report and recommend management of carbon emissions. We currently have a portfolio greening policy which encourages customers to green their businesses. For example, Access Bank issued the first green bond in Nigeria in 2018. Funds received from the climate bond initiative was managed efficiently to support sustainable business. We also have a renewable energy product which supports development of solar power. The Climate bond instrument also helped provide homes for 400 people displaced by flood in Lagos, Nigeria, thus helping in physical, economic development and employment.

Interviewer: What barriers have you identified in these initiatives?

Respondent 3: Other banks really need to key into the sustainable principle as we always lose customers to our competitors who let them have their way without recommending or suggesting ways to protect the environment that they operate in. There is a lot of knowledge gap among entrepreneurs, banking staff and the government.

Interviewer: How can these barriers be mitigated?

Respondent 3: Well, lots of awareness is needed, as well as policy shifts which punish offenders and reward greening such as tax rebates, funding etc. Also, it is essential to pair new start-ups with experts.

Interviewer: What kind of credit products are available for green companies?

Respondent 3: We have available funding for green companies for example, the funding from climate bond instruments and also other credit facilities which allow you access credit at competitive rates.

Interviewer: What kind of products are available for start-up green companies?

Respondent 3: This is on a case-to-case basis. We have to analyse the projected cash flow and profitability projection from the start-up as well as a possible pair-up with experts.

Interviewer: Do you offer financial loans to construction companies? What are the major risks that you have identified in lending to construction companies?

Respondent 3: Ofcourse, the construction industry is a major segment for credit engagement as they form the basis for infrastructure and development. However, the risks faced are diversion risk, operational risk, market risk due to fluctuating prices of raw materials or products ,and environmental risk.

Interviewer: How can these risks be mitigated?

Respondent 3: There is effective loan monitoring. Also as explained earlier, our climate experts develop an EIA report which we use to carefully guide the customer on his operations.

Interviewer: Have you processed a credit facility for a recycling company before now?

Respondent 3: Well, I am very sure that we have recyclers in our books, but frankly, we have been more proactive in the renewable energy space.

Interviewer: What are the risks you encountered and the mitigants?

Respondent 3: Refer to question above. However, I think the operational and market risk will be particularly important. How good will the acceptability of their products be?

Interviewer: What criteria would make the bank accept to lend to a start-up recycling company?

Respondent 3: The business has to be viable and profitable, and they must meet up to our risk acceptance criteria.

Interviewer: In your opinion, do you see recycling as a viable business that a commercial institution would be interested in investing in?

Respondent 3: Yes, I believe this is an emerging sector which has multiple benefits such as environmental management, and socio- economic growth. Consequently, in addition to the attraction of profits, this can be part of the organization's CSR policy. As long as it is bankable, it is viable.

Interviewer: Is there anything else you might want to add?

Respondent 3: Nigeria must do more to meet up to its climate commitments, however, this cannot be done without inputs from the government and the financial space. A lot of sensitization is needed to aid the targets we have set for ourselves, and innovative ideas and technology are needed for success. Thank you.

APPENDIX 3.1 PARTICIPANT AGREEMENT FORM – RESPONDENT 3

Participant Agreement Form

The title of the research project

Promoting a circular economy through plastic recycling. What is the feasibility and environmental impact of using plastic recycled products for building in Abuja, Nigeria?

Name, position and contact details of researcher

Ugochi Emeka-okanu, Graduate Green Economy Student at Bournemouth University
 Contact at – ugookanu@gmail.com

Name, position and contact details of supervisor

Tilak Ginige, Senior Lecturer in Environmental Law
 Contact at – tginige@bournemouth.ac.uk

To be completed prior to data collection activity

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<p>I understand that my data may be included in an anonymised form within a dataset to be archived at BU's Online Research Data Repository</p>

I understand that my data may be used in an anonymised form by the research team to support other research projects in the future, including future publications, reports or presentations	
	Initial box to agree
I consent to take part in the project on the basis set out above (Section A)	

I confirm my agreement to take part in the project on the basis set out above.

<u>Gbenga Adedeke</u> Name of participant (BLOCK CAPITALS)	<u>20/07/2021</u> Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	<u>GA</u> Signature
<u>UGOCHI EMEKA-OKANU</u> Name of researcher (BLOCK CAPITALS)	<u>20/07/2021</u> Date (dd/mm/yyyy)	<u>[Signature]</u> Signature